

Should VAT be booked in the companies' P&L reports?

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ABSTRACT

VAT is usually being presented as an indirect tax on consumers, but it is just as fair to refer to it as a *direct* tax on companies' margins, as already demonstrated in the economic literature.

From this angle, VAT has an impact on the profitability of businesses: in the field of accounting, therefore, it becomes logical to recommend a VAT-included approach of the P&L.

Key words: Financial analysis, Accounting, P&L, Income statement, VAT, Taxes

1. INTRODUCTION

The Value-Added Tax or VAT is usually presented as an indirect tax on consumption, given its potential impact on market prices.

But it is equally accurate to describe it as a *direct* tax on corporate margins, as already demonstrated in the economic literature, notably by Murray Rothbard (2009) and Pascal Salin (2014). From this angle, VAT has an impact not only on the profitability of companies, but also on social production structures.

In the fields of accounting and financial analysis, consequently, it becomes logical to incorporate the VAT into the P&L report. Indeed, income statements are traditionally established net of VAT, concealing important information on profitability calculations.

2. THE MECHANISM OF VAT

Introduced in France in the 50's, VAT makes it possible to eliminate the risk of a cascading taxation caused by taxes on simple sales. This anomaly would occur in all the production cycles carried out by a chain of separate companies: the goods and services in production would then be taxed each time they change hands.

To remedy this inconvenience, VAT, as its name suggests, is a tax on the "value added": in accounting, this is materialized as the difference between revenues and external expenses.

Concretely, VAT on sales is "collected" and that on external purchases is "deductible", the difference (clearing balance) being paid to the tax authorities. For each product sold to a final consumer, VAT is therefore collected by all companies that contribute to the production process, from the raw material extraction company to the final distributor.

The impact of VAT on market prices

The final consumer, on the other hand, does not have the option to recover VAT, which is one of the reasons why VAT is often considered to be a tax on consumption.

In general, it is true that there is an impact of VAT (or similar sales taxes) on retail prices. This is obvious for products such as tobacco or fuel, for which excise duties are superimposed on VAT. At such a level of taxation, producers and retailers have no choice but to "pass on" taxes to the selling prices, unless they abandon their activity and leave the market.

Although a variation of the rate of VAT eventually has an impact on prices, it is important to note that this is not a mechanical phenomenon. In the traditional view of accounting, price

fixing is sometimes represented as the simple addition of a price excluding taxes to which VAT is added, but in reality, a market price is the result of the confrontation of supply and demand, sometimes on a worldwide market.

In other words, a business owner will not necessarily be able to pass on a tax increase to the selling prices and, initially, the margins of his business will tighten. Conversely, in the case of a reduction in VAT, if the market and competition allow it, he may decide to keep its prices unchanged in order to increase his margins.

As an example, the reduction in the VAT rate on restaurants in 2009 in France did not lead to a mechanical decrease in prices in the sector (cf. Salin 2014, chap. 7). By contrast, the restaurant owners have kept their hands on prices... within the limits imposed by the "invisible hand" of the market. Some owners promised price reductions, while others preferred to commit to job creations.

Who pays VAT?

The above examples illustrate the fact that VAT has an impact on companies' margins, before possibly being passed on to prices.

In the economic literature, this mechanism has already been demonstrated, notably by Murray Rothbard (2009, 930–34; 1156–62) and Pascal Salin (2014, chap. 5).

So, who pays VAT then? To answer this question, it is useful to view a company as a group of individuals – shareholders, lenders, employees, external service providers etc. – linked together by contracts and contributing to the value added. As noted by Pascal Salin (2014, chap. 8), the notion of “corporate taxes” is therefore a language abuse: taxes are collected by companies, but in the end, they are necessarily paid by individuals. Therefore, it is not possible to precisely measure the proportion in which the different actors of the company bear the burden of VAT, all of them being also consumers of goods and services. According to Murray Rothbard (2010), in the short term, an increase in VAT is likely to weigh on profits and wages, before eventually being passed on to prices, and thus to consumers. And in the opposite case of a tax reduction not reflected in prices, a business owner may choose to increase his profit, or the salaries of his employees, or to reinvest the surpluses collected to improve the quality of his products.

The impact of VAT on businesses

It should be noted here that VAT weighs on companies' margins even before we can verify the profitability of businesses. Value added, which serves as the base for this tax, is then being

distributed in the form of wages, interests and profits, or partially retained. In economics textbooks, value added is thus often presented, as the compensation of the factors of production. Without VAT, it is therefore quite conceivable that certain activities, which were abandoned yesterday, would become profitable today.

According to Murray Rothbard (2010), VAT can also have an impact on the structure of the labor market: as an example, Rothbard mentions the use of external service providers, making it possible to deduct VAT from invoices, which is of course not the case for internal employees. As a result, companies may have to make organizational choices involving more or less outsourcing, depending on the level of VAT.

3. VAT IN THE P&L REPORT

In accounting, the P&L report is traditionally presented net of VAT, that is, revenues and purchases being expressed excluding VAT. VAT, on the other hand, is booked directly in the balance sheet. This reflects the misconception that a company only collects VAT, this process supposedly having no impact on its profitability.

First, it should be noted that this accounting treatment increases the difficulty of reconciliations in cash flow analyses, since sales and purchases are realized including VAT, before the VAT clearing balance is returned to the tax authorities. Therefore, there is always a risk of confusion between, on the one hand, sales and purchases recorded excluding VAT in the income statement, and on the other hand, trade receivables and supplier debts recorded including VAT in the balance sheet.

Second and more importantly, including VAT in the income statement would make it possible to accurately measure its impact on profitability.

By way of illustration, let's imagine a company that, during the year 2023, buys for 60 k€ incl. VAT of raw materials, before transforming and reselling them in the form of finished goods for 120 k€ incl. VAT. Let us assume that this company is being taxed at a VAT rate of 20%, but that this rate is being reduced to 10% by the tax administration in 2024. Let us also assume that in the short term, all other things are being equal: concretely, this means that the state of the market allows the increase in VAT to be passed on to retail prices, so that prices including VAT remain unchanged; supply and demand levels in terms of quantity of goods and services also remain unchanged. This example is comparable to the situation mentioned above on restaurants in France in 2009.

Here is the result for this company in the form of a simplified P&L report including VAT:

P&L incl. VAT (k€)	2023	2024	Δ 2024/2023
<i>VAT rate</i>	20%	10%	-10%
Revenues incl. VAT	120	120	0
External expenses incl. VAT	-60	-60	0
Gross Value Added	60	60	0
<i>Gross Value Added / Revenues incl. VAT</i>	50%	50%	0%
Collected VAT on Sales	-20.0	-10.9	9.1
Deductible VAT on Expenses	10.0	5.5	-4.5
Net Value Added	50.0	54.5	4.5
<i>Net Value Added / Revenues incl. VAT</i>	41.7%	45.5%	3.8%

Figure 1. P&L report incl. VAT (k€)

By hypothesis, the activity is stable, as reflected in the level of revenues and purchases. From one year to the other, only the amount of VAT clearing balance changes, i.e., a difference of 4.5 k€, having a direct impact on the Net Value Added.

Here is now the traditional presentation of the income statement, net of VAT:

P&L net of VAT (k€)	2023	2024	Δ 2024/2023
<i>VAT rate</i>	20%	10%	-10%
Revenues excl. VAT	100.0	109.1	9.1
Cost of Sales excl. VAT	-50.0	-54.5	-4.5
Net Value Added	50.0	54.5	4.5
<i>Net Value Added / Revenues excl. VAT</i>	50%	50%	0%

Figure 2. P&L report excl. VAT (k€)

Although the final margin is indeed up 4.5 k€, the above P&L does not allow to highlight the origin of the increase, attributing it erroneously to a rise in the activity, while by hypothesis we assumed the stability of supply, demand, and retail prices (prices including VAT). In addition, the margin rate displayed here is stable, which is not consistent with the rise in profitability observed in the first table (+3.8 points).

So, this example demonstrates that it is important to display VAT flows in operating accounts, in order to give a fair representation of its impact on profitability.

4. ADDITIONAL REMARKS

Let us also note that the inclusion of VAT in revenues would also be justified from a statistical point of view : The French National Institute of Statistics and Economic Studies (INSEE) is not mistaken by reintegrating VAT in its calculation of Gross Domestic Product, equal to the sum of Value Added and VAT.

The previous example highlights the impact of VAT on margins in the event of a change in VAT rates. But at constant VAT, similar examples could be applied to show that VAT is not neutral in profitability calculations. There are indeed four VAT rates today in France, depending on the nature of the goods and services traded, ranging from 2.1% to 20%. A restaurant owner can thus be exposed to three VAT rates: 10% on on-site catering, 5.5% on takeaway sales and 20% on possible training workshops. Regarding multinationals and export sales, it is generally the purchaser who is taxed at the rate applicable in his country. And for external purchases, VAT is usually deductible, which is not the case for integrated production. *Therefore, for all*

companies subject to different VAT rates, an analysis of the income statement including VAT by segment would highlight a differentiated impact on margins.

In the absence of a change in accounting standards, it would thus be beneficial for companies to keep an internal reporting that would include VAT in the P&L reports.

5. CONCLUSION

The confusion around VAT, when only viewed as a consumption tax, probably comes from the fact that its amount is indicated on invoices: in reality, this information is aiming at companies reusing purchases in their production cycles, which are therefore able to deduct VAT from their purchase costs. But if one assumes that only final consumers bear the burden of VAT, one should also assume that, by paying a market price, consumers only bear costs, without the benefit of the goods and services purchased in return.

In reality, the impact of VAT is not neutral for businesses. The example presented above has demonstrated this, by describing the consequences of a reduction in VAT on the P&L reports. The integration of VAT into P&L reports and financial analyses is therefore necessary to measure its impact on the profitability of companies.

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